

Comparative Performance of Nonlinear and Traditional Input-Output Models: A Case Study of Kazakhstan

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Abstract. The paper develops a nonlinear input-output model for analyzing medium-term changes in production networks under external shocks. The theoretical framework is formulated for a general class of neoclassical production functions and combines an optimal resource-allocation problem with Young dual equilibrium price equations. Unlike the classical linear input-output balance with fixed coefficients, the proposed approach allows endogenous changes in technological coefficients caused by shifts in relative prices and substitution effects.

For the applied analysis, a model with nested Cobb-Douglas-CES technologies is constructed for Kazakhstan using official symmetric input-output tables. Identification and calibration of the model provide estimates of substitution elasticities for aggregated sectoral complexes of the economy. The model is then tested on input-output data for 2012-2024 and compared with the linear Cobb-Douglas balance model. The numerical results show that the nonlinear model provides more accurate medium-term reconstruction, especially for sectors with more flexible substitution mechanisms.

Keywords: Input-output model · Production networks · Resource allocation · Young duality · CES production functions · Kazakhstan economy

1 Introduction

Input-output analysis is a standard mathematical tool for studying intersectoral interactions and shock propagation in production networks. Its theoretical basis is the classical linear input-output model of Leontief [1], where the gross output vector $Y = (Y_1, \dots, Y_m)$ is distributed between intermediate consumption AY and final demand X^0 through a nonnegative matrix of direct input coefficients A [1]. The practical importance of the Leontief framework is closely connected

with the availability of statistical input-output tables included in the internationally standardized System of National Accounts [2]. This availability explains why linear input-output models remain widely used for empirical analysis and forecasting based on publicly available statistical databases of many countries.

The main limitation of the classical approach is the assumption that the matrix of direct input coefficients remains fixed over time. Economically, this corresponds to zero substitution elasticity between production inputs. Criticism of this assumption dates back to Solow's work on substitution between labor and capital in growth models [3]. Since the late twentieth century, empirical studies have demonstrated that substitution between inputs becomes significant even for medium-term horizons due to technological changes and increasing diversity of goods and services [4]. Recent empirical evidence also indicates substantial dependence of input-output coefficients on relative price dynamics [5]. This makes nonlinear input-output models with endogenous technological coefficients a natural extension of the classical framework.

Recent global supply-chain shocks have made nonlinear production-network models especially relevant. In [6, 7] propagation of shocks is studied within a multisector general-equilibrium framework with Cobb-Douglas production technologies corresponding to unit substitution elasticities. Further developments based on nested CES production structures were proposed in [8, 9]. However, inter-industry balance analysis in these papers typically relies on local linearization and therefore does not fully describe nonlinear changes in input-output coefficients.

A theoretical framework for nonlinear input-output analysis based on neo-classical production functions and their Young-dual unit cost functions was proposed in [10]. In this approach, equilibrium intersectoral relations are described by a resource-allocation problem together with a dual price system constructed from unit cost functions. Unlike the classical linear balance model, this nonlinear equilibrium framework allows direct input coefficients to change endogenously in response to equilibrium price variations while accounting for input substitution elasticities. This makes it possible to analyze changes in input-output tables under alternative external economic scenarios.

In our previous studies, aggregated nonlinear input-output models with CES production functions were applied to the Kazakhstan economy for analysis of pandemic supply shocks and tax-policy scenarios [11],[12]. However, calibration of these models was previously performed on relatively short statistical intervals. This leaves open the question of to what extent the nonlinear framework improves reconstruction of input-output statistics compared with the classical linear approach and how stable such models remain on broader empirical data sets.

The present paper addresses these questions for the Kazakhstan economy using aggregated input-output tables for 2012-2024. We consider a nonlinear equilibrium model with nested Cobb-Douglas-CES (CD-CES) production functions, where some primary resources may be separated into the Cobb-Douglas component, while the remaining intermediate and primary inputs form the CES

aggregate. The model is identified from the base year input-output table and calibrated using Kazakhstan statistical data.

The paper aims to compare reconstruction properties of nonlinear and linear input-output models for medium-term periods, including the years associated with the COVID-19 shock and supply-chain disruptions. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly summarizes the nonlinear equilibrium framework developed in previous papers and presents, in a unified form, the corresponding duality representation together with results on existence, uniqueness, and stability of equilibrium prices. Section 3 introduces the aggregated Kazakhstan input-output database, specifies the nested CD-CES production structure and the corresponding equilibrium evaluation procedure, and describes the calibration process. The final part of Section 3 compares reconstruction errors for nonlinear and linear input-output models based on Kazakhstan statistical data.

2 Mathematical Framework

In this section, we briefly review the results of [10, 13] and present the general form of the nonlinear input-output model together with its equilibrium analysis. We consider a multisectoral economy with m sectors. Each sector produces a homogeneous good that can be used both as an intermediate input and for final consumption. In the production of domestic goods, n primary resources that are not produced by sectors are also utilized. The economy is supposed to be open with respect to primary resources. This implies that sectors can freely purchase them for intermediate consumption at exogenously given prices determined on external markets.

Economic agents of the production network consist of a representative consumer, whose preferences are described by a utility function, and a representative producer in each sector characterized by the production function.

2.1 Primal Problem and Optimality Conditions

Variables and technologies. Let $X_j^i \geq 0$ denote the amount of good j used in sector i , and let $X_j^0 \geq 0$ denote the amount of good j allocated to final consumption. Denote³

$$X^i = (X_1^i, \dots, X_m^i) \in \mathbb{R}_+^m, \quad X^0 = (X_1^0, \dots, X_m^0) \in \mathbb{R}_+^m, \quad i = 1, \dots, m.$$

Production in sector i is described by the production function $F_i(X^i, l^i)$, where $l^i = (l_1^i, \dots, l_n^i) \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ is the vector of primary resources used by sector i . We suppose that each primary resource is used by at least one sector.

Final consumption is described by the utility function $F_0(X^0)$. Let $p_0 > 0$ be the scale parameter translating utility into monetary units.

³ We denote by \mathbb{R}_+^m and \mathbb{R}_{++}^m the sets of nonnegative and strictly positive vectors in \mathbb{R}^m , respectively.

All production functions F_i , $i = 1, \dots, m$, and the utility function F_0 are nonnegative, concave, monotonically nondecreasing, positively homogeneous of degree one, and satisfy $F_i(0) = 0$, $F_0(0) = 0$. In addition, all goods are assumed essential for the representative consumer, i.e. $F_0(X^0) > 0$ for all $X^0 \neq 0$. Throughout the paper, functions with these properties are called *neoclassical*. These assumptions are standard in production theory and are satisfied by the specifications used in Section 3.

Feasibility set. Material balance constraints take the form

$$\sum_{i=1}^m X_j^i + X_j^0 \leq F_j(X^j, l^j), \quad j = 1, \dots, m, \quad (1)$$

while primary resources satisfy

$$\sum_{i=1}^m l_k^i \leq \bar{l}_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, n. \quad (2)$$

All variables are assumed nonnegative:

$$X_j^0 \geq 0, \quad X^j \geq 0, \quad l^j \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \quad (3)$$

Productivity. We assume that the economy is productive, i.e. there exists a feasible allocation such that

$$F_j(X^j, l^j) > \sum_{i=1}^m X_j^i, \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \quad (4)$$

Economically, this means that the production system can generate positive final output beyond intermediate requirements.

Primal problem. The optimal allocation problem is

$$\max_{X^0, X, l \geq 0} p_0 F_0(X^0) \quad (5)$$

subject to constraints (1)-(3).

Lagrangian and KKT conditions. Introduce multipliers $p = (p_1, \dots, p_m) \in \mathbb{R}_+^m$ for material balances and $s = (s_1, \dots, s_n) \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ for primary resources. The Lagrangian is

$$\mathcal{L} = p_0 F_0(X^0) + \sum_{j=1}^m p_j \left(F_j(X^j, l^j) - \sum_{i=0}^m X_j^i \right) + \sum_{k=1}^n s_k \left(\bar{l}_k - \sum_{i=1}^m l_k^i \right). \quad (6)$$

Condition (4) is a Slater-type condition for problem (5). Hence the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions are necessary and sufficient.

Theorem 1 ([10]). *A feasible allocation $\{\hat{X}^0, \hat{X}^1, \dots, \hat{X}^m, \hat{l}^1, \dots, \hat{l}^m\}$ satisfying (1)-(3) is a solution to problem (5) if and only if there exist multipliers $p \in \mathbb{R}_+^m$, $s \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ such that⁴*

$$(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) \in \arg \max \{ p_j F_j(X^j, l^j) - p \cdot X^j - s \cdot l^j \}, \quad j = 1, \dots, m, \quad (7)$$

⁴ $x \cdot y$ denotes the scalar product of vectors x and y .

and

$$\hat{X}^0 \in \arg \max \{p_0 F_0(X^0) - p \cdot X^0\}; \quad (8)$$

moreover, the complementarity conditions hold:

$$p_j \left(F_j(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) - \hat{X}_j^0 - \sum_{i=1}^m \hat{X}_j^i \right) = 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, m, \quad (9)$$

$$s_k \left(\bar{l}_k - \sum_{i=1}^m \hat{l}_k^i \right) = 0, \quad k = 1, \dots, n. \quad (10)$$

Remark 1. The conditions of Theorem 1 admit the standard interpretation of a competitive equilibrium: sectors maximize profits at given prices p , s , the representative consumer maximizes utility, and complementarity conditions correspond to market clearing.

2.2 Young Dual Problem and Competitive Equilibrium

Introduce the Young transforms of the production and utility functions [10]. For each sector $j = 1, \dots, m$, define the unit cost function

$$q_j(p, s) = \inf \left\{ \frac{pX^j + sl^j}{F_j(X^j, l^j)} \mid X^j \geq 0, l^j \geq 0, F_j(X^j, l^j) > 0 \right\}. \quad (11)$$

Similarly, define the consumption price index

$$q_0(p) = \inf \left\{ \frac{pX^0}{F_0(X^0)} \mid X^0 \geq 0, F_0(X^0) > 0 \right\}. \quad (12)$$

The functions q_j and q_0 inherit the class of F_j and F_0 , i.e. they are neoclassical in the terminology introduced above.

The following theorem reformulates the corresponding duality representation result of [10] in the notation of the present model.

Theorem 2. *Let $(\hat{X}^0, \hat{X}, \hat{l})$ be a solution of the resource allocation problem, and let $(\hat{p}, \hat{s}) \geq 0$ be Lagrange multipliers satisfying the optimality conditions of Theorem 1. Then $\hat{p} \geq 0$ solves the problem*

$$q_0(p) \longrightarrow \sup_{p \geq 0}, \quad (13)$$

$$q_j(p, \hat{s}) \geq p_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \quad (14)$$

Problem (13)-(14) we call the *Young dual problem* associated with the resource allocation model.

Following [13], we impose the following assumptions:

(i) (*Economic productivity*) For the given $p_0 > 0$ and $s \in \mathbb{R}_{++}^n$, there exist $\hat{X}^0 \geq 0$ and $\{(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) \geq 0\}_{j=1}^m$ such that productivity condition (4) holds and

$$F_0(\hat{X}^0) > 0, \quad p_0 F_0(\hat{X}^0) \geq s \cdot \sum_{j=1}^m \hat{l}^j.$$

(ii) (*Indecomposability*) For every feasible allocation satisfying (1),

$$\hat{X}_j^0 > 0 \text{ for some } j \implies F_i(\hat{X}^i, \hat{l}^i) > 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, m.$$

(iii) (*Reference equilibrium*) There exist $(\bar{p}, \bar{s}) \in \mathbb{R}_{++}^{m+n}$ such that

$$q_j(\bar{p}, \bar{s}) = \bar{p}_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, m.$$

(iv) (*No complete substitution*) $F_j(X^j, 0) = 0$ for all $X^j \in \mathbb{R}_+^m$, $j = 1, \dots, m$.

Assumptions (i)-(ii) exclude economically degenerate equilibria and imply $q_j(p, s) = p_j$ for equilibrium prices. Assumption (iii) corresponds to existence of a benchmark equilibrium state and naturally holds in applications with normalized price indices. Assumption (iv) excludes production without primary resources and guarantees uniqueness of equilibrium prices.

Based on Theorem 5 in [13], the following statement holds.

Proposition 1. *Let assumptions (i)-(iv) hold. Then, for every $s \in \mathbb{R}_{++}^n$, there exists a unique vector $\hat{p} = \hat{p}(s) \in \mathbb{R}_{++}^m$ satisfying*

$$q_j(\hat{p}, s) = \hat{p}_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \quad (15)$$

Moreover, the dependence of $\hat{p}(s)$ on s is Lipschitz stable in the sense of [13].

Combining Theorem 1 and Proposition 1, we obtain the following result.

Theorem 3 (Existence of competitive equilibrium). *Let F_0 and F_j , $j = 1, \dots, m$, be neoclassical functions and assumptions (i)-(iv) hold. Then there exists a competitive equilibrium $\{\hat{X}^0, \hat{X}^1, \dots, \hat{X}^m, \hat{l}^1, \dots, \hat{l}^m, \hat{p}, \hat{s}\}$, where $\hat{X}^0 \geq 0$, $\hat{X}^0 \neq 0$, $\{(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) \geq 0\}_{j=1}^m$, $\hat{p} > 0$, $\hat{s} > 0$, and $F_j(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) > 0$ for $j = 1, \dots, m$.*

2.3 Interindustry Balance

Under the conditions of Theorem 3, we derive the interindustry balance relations corresponding to a competitive equilibrium.

Proposition 2. *Let $\{\hat{X}^0, \hat{X}^1, \dots, \hat{X}^m, \hat{l}^1, \dots, \hat{l}^m, \hat{p}, \hat{s}\}$ be a competitive equilibrium and denote $\hat{F} = (F_1(\hat{X}^1, \hat{l}^1), \dots, F_m(\hat{X}^m, \hat{l}^m)) \in \mathbb{R}_{++}^m$. Then*

(i) *Equilibrium inputs satisfy⁵*

$$(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) \in F_j(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) \partial q_j(\hat{p}, \hat{s}). \quad (16)$$

(ii) *The matrix $\hat{A}(\hat{p}) = \|\hat{\lambda}_{ij}(\hat{p})\|_{i,j=1}^m$, where $\hat{\lambda}_{ij}(\hat{p}) = \hat{X}_i^j / F_j(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) \geq 0$ is productive, i.e. $(I - \hat{A}(\hat{p}))^{-1} \geq 0$.*

(iii) *The equilibrium allocation satisfies the interindustry balance relation⁶*

$$\hat{F} = (I - \hat{A}(\hat{p}))^{-1} \hat{X}^0. \quad (17)$$

⁵ we denote ∂q a superdifferential of a concave function q .

⁶ where I is the identity matrix.

Proof (Sketch of proof). Relation (16) follows from the Young duality characterization of optimal inputs. Together with Euler’s identity for positively homogeneous cost functions, it implies productivity of $\hat{A}^T(\hat{p})$ and therefore of $\hat{A}(\hat{p})$.

Since $\hat{p}_j > 0$, complementarity conditions (9) imply $F_j(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) = \sum_{i=1}^m \hat{X}_j^i + \hat{X}_j^0$, $j = 1, \dots, m$. Hence $\hat{F} = \hat{A}(\hat{p})\hat{F} + \hat{X}^0$, and productivity of $\hat{A}(\hat{p})$ gives (17).

3 Application of the Model

To obtain an applied version of the model, we specify production functions and construct a database for identification and calibration.

The standard empirical basis for input-output analysis is provided by symmetric input-output tables published within the system of national accounts [2]. Since prices in the model are endogenous, we use tables in current prices as compiled by statistical agencies.

3.1 Symmetric Input-Output Tables

General Form of a Symmetric Input-Output Table A symmetric input-output table has the three-quadrant structure presented in Table 1. The first quadrant represents intermediate consumption across industries, the second corresponds to final demand, and the third describes primary inputs [1]. Here, Z_i^j

Table 1. General structure of a symmetric input-output table

	Intermediate consumption	Final demand	Total output
Industries	$Z_i^j, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, m$	$Z_j^0, \quad j = 1, \dots, m$	Y_j
Primary inputs	$Z_{m+k}^j, \quad k = 1, \dots, n$		
Total output	Y_i		

denotes intermediate deliveries from sector i to sector j , Z_j^0 denotes final demand for sector j , and Z_{m+k}^j represents expenditures on primary inputs by sector j . The quantities Y_j denote gross outputs of industries. By construction, the table is balanced: for each sector, total output equals both total supply (row sum) and total production costs (column sum).

Using the notation of Table 1, define the matrices $A = \|a_{ij}\|$ and $B = \|b_{kj}\|$ of intermediate and primary input coefficients, where

$$a_{ij} = \frac{Z_i^j}{Y_j}, \quad b_{kj} = \frac{Z_{m+k}^j}{Y_j} \quad i, j = 1, \dots, m, \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (18)$$

By construction,

$$\sum_{i=1}^m a_{ij} + \sum_{k=1}^n b_{kj} = 1, \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \quad (19)$$

Aggregated Input-Output Database of Kazakhstan We use aggregated symmetric input-output tables of Kazakhstan for 2012-2024 as the empirical basis for calibration and comparison of the models.

Due to the export-oriented structure of the Kazakhstani economy, industries are aggregated into four sectoral complexes according to their relation to foreign trade and final consumption (see Appendix, Table 5): Manufacturing, Exporting, Infrastructure, and Services. These complexes preserve the dominant interindustry linkages of the original tables.

The aggregated input-output table for Kazakhstan for 2023 is presented in Appendix, Table 6. In quadrant III, “Import” denotes imported intermediate inputs, “Wage” labor compensation, and “Gross operating surplus”(GOS) the residual part of value added after wages, treated as an aggregated capital-related primary input.

3.2 Linear Input-Output Model: Cobb-Douglas Specification

Since the middle of last century, the linear Leontief input-output model [1] has been used to analyze the response of sectoral outputs to changes in final demand through multipliers determined by the productive matrix $(I - A)^{-1} \geq 0$, where $A \geq 0$ is the matrix of fixed intermediate input coefficients (18), traditionally constructed from input-output tables in constant prices.

When the coefficients (18) of matrices A and B are computed from symmetric input-output tables in current prices, as described in Section 3.1, the resulting model corresponds to the Cobb-Douglas specification with constant equilibrium cost shares [6]. The balance equation takes the same linear form

$$Y = (I - A)^{-1} Z^0, \quad (20)$$

where $Y \geq 0$ is the gross output vector and $Z^0 \geq 0$ is the final demand vector, both measured in current prices. Together, (18) and (20) completely determine the linear Cobb-Douglas input-output model.

The main limitation of the linear framework is that the matrices A and B remain fixed under changes in relative prices and economic conditions. Therefore, the model does not capture substitution effects and equilibrium restructuring of intermediate input proportions.

3.3 Nonlinear Input-Output Model: Equilibrium Evaluation

Unlike the linear input-output framework with fixed technological coefficients, the nonlinear model determines intermediate and primary input coefficients endogenously through equilibrium prices and production technologies. Following Section 2, we specify a parametric class of production functions.

Nested Cobb-Douglas-CES Specification For empirical applications, we use nested Cobb-Douglas-CES (CD-CES) production functions. CES technologies

correspond to constant elasticity of substitution, while nested specifications allow different substitution between groups of inputs. We consider

$$F_j(X, l) = \alpha_j G_j^{\gamma_j} \prod_{k=1}^n l_{kj}^{(1-\theta_{kj})b_{kj}}, \quad (21)$$

where

$$G_j(X, l) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m a_{ij} X_{ij}^{-\rho_j} + \sum_{k=1}^n \theta_{kj} b_{kj} l_{kj}^{-\rho_j} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\rho_j}}, \quad (22)$$

$$\alpha_j = \gamma_j^{-\gamma_j} \prod_{k=1}^n b_{kj}^{-(1-\theta_{kj})b_{kj}}, \quad \gamma_j = \sum_{i=1}^m a_{ij} + \sum_{k=1}^n \theta_{kj} b_{kj}. \quad (23)$$

Parameters a_{ij} and b_{kj} are the Cobb-Douglas proportions introduced in (18). Parameters ρ_j determine the elasticity of substitution $\sigma_j = (1 + \rho_j)^{-1}$, where $-1 \leq \rho_j < +\infty$, and the case $\rho_j = 0$ is defined by the corresponding limit with Cobb-Douglas proportions.

The parameters θ_{kj} distinguish primary factors entering the CES aggregate: $\theta_{kj} = 0$ corresponds to unit substitution elasticity with the remaining factors, while $\theta_{kj} = 1$ means that factor k belongs to the CES aggregate.

Specifications (21)-(23) imply the following form of the cost functions:

$$q_j(p, s) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{a_{ij}}{\gamma_j} p_i^{\frac{\rho_j}{\rho_j+1}} + \sum_{k=1}^n \theta_{kj} \frac{b_{kj}}{\gamma_j} s_k^{\frac{\rho_j}{\rho_j+1}} \right)^{\gamma_j \frac{1+\rho_j}{\rho_j}} \prod_{k=1}^n s_k^{(1-\theta_{kj})b_{kj}}. \quad (24)$$

Equation (24) determines the explicit form of system (15) for equilibrium prices. Since the minimizers in (11) are unique in this case, the cost functions $q_j(p, s)$ are differentiable and (16) becomes

$$(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) = F_j(\hat{X}^j, \hat{l}^j) \nabla q_j(\hat{p}, \hat{s}). \quad (25)$$

Competitive Equilibrium Using the notation of Table 1, define allocations in current prices by

$$Z_j^0 = p_j X_j^0, \quad Y_j = p_j F_j(X^j, l^j), \quad (26)$$

$$Z_i^j = p_i X_i^j, \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad Z_{m+k}^j = s_k l_k^j, \quad k = 1, \dots, n. \quad (27)$$

The following statement is a corollary of Propositions 1 and 2.

Proposition 3. *In the case of nested CD-CES production functions, for every $s > 0$, system (15) with cost functions (24) has a unique solution $p = p(s)$ corresponding to equilibrium prices.*

The equilibrium allocation satisfies

$$Y = (I - \Lambda(p))^{-1} Z^0, \quad (28)$$

where

$$\lambda_{ij} = a_{ij} \left(\frac{p_i}{p_j} \right)^{\frac{\rho_j}{1+\rho_j}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{s_k}{p_j} \right)^{(1-\theta_{kj})b_{kj}/\gamma_j} \right)^{\frac{\rho_j}{1+\rho_j}}. \quad (29)$$

Equilibrium intermediate and primary inputs are given by

$$Z_i^j = \lambda_{ij} Y_j, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, m, \quad (30)$$

$$Z_{m+k}^j = \beta_{kj} Y_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, m, \quad k = 1, \dots, n, \quad (31)$$

where

$$\beta_{kj} = (1 - \theta_{kj})b_{kj} + \theta_{kj}b_{kj} \left(\frac{s_k}{p_j} \right)^{\frac{\rho_j}{1+\rho_j}} \left(\prod_{t=1}^n \left(\frac{s_t}{p_j} \right)^{(1-\theta_{tj})b_{tj}/\gamma_j} \right)^{\frac{\rho_j}{1+\rho_j}}.$$

Remark 2. Fixing a base-year input-output table in current prices and identifying matrices A and B from these data, Proposition 3 reproduces quadrants I and III of the table for the given final demand vector Z^0 and normalized prices $p = s = 1$ for arbitrary substitution elasticities $\rho_j, j = 1, \dots, m$.

Remark 2 implies that Assumption (iii) of section 2.2 holds.

Proposition 3 yields the following equilibrium evaluation procedure.

Algorithm for Model Evaluation Fix a base-year symmetric input-output table in current prices and identify parameters (18) of the CD-CES production functions (21).

For a target year, specify primary-resource price indices $s \in \mathbb{R}_{++}^n$, final demand vector $Z^0 \in \mathbb{R}_+^m$, and substitution elasticities $\rho_j, j = 1, \dots, m$.

Then compute equilibrium prices from (15) with (24), evaluate $\Lambda(p)$ from (29), compute gross outputs Y from (28), and recover quadrants I and III of the input-output table from (30)-(31).

Remark 3. Explicit specification of the utility function F_0 is not required for equilibrium evaluation under given scenario conditions; only existence of a utility function satisfying the assumptions of Section 2 is needed.

The following calibration procedure provides verification of substitution elasticities ρ_j using multi-period statistical data.

3.4 Calibration of the Model

The empirical input-output database of Kazakhstan for 2012-2024 introduced in Section 3.1 is used to calibrate substitution elasticities ρ_j . Since CES elasticities are assumed constant, the model is mainly suitable for short- and medium-term analysis. We therefore use 2017-2020 and 2024 for calibration, excluding 2021-2022 as years affected by the COVID-19 shock. The remaining years 2012-2016 and 2021-2022 are used to test the model outside the calibration interval.

Recall that the aggregated production network of Kazakhstan consists of four sectoral complexes and three primary resources: Import, Wage, and Gross

operating surplus (GOS). Thus, $m = 4$ and $n = 3$. We assume that the Wage resource enters the Cobb-Douglas component of the production function, while the remaining aggregated inputs form the CES aggregate. Accordingly, in (21)-(24), we set $\theta_2 = 0$, while $\theta_1 = \theta_3 = 1$. This assumption gives the best calibration results among the considered specifications.

The base year is 2023. The matrices A and B are computed from the base-year input-output table (see Appendix, Table 6) by (18). Scenario data for 2012-2024, including final demand vectors and primary-resource price indices, are presented in Appendix, Table 7. Here, s_1 corresponds to the dollar-to-tenge exchange-rate index, s_2 to the index of nominal average annual wages, and s_3 to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) deflator index.

The main objective of the numerical analysis is to compare the nonlinear input-output framework with the linear model discussed in Section 3.2. In both cases, the models reconstruct equilibrium gross outputs corresponding to observed final demand vectors. We formulate calibration as minimization of the maximal relative deviation of gross outputs across complexes:

$$\min_{\rho} \max_{t,j} \left| \frac{Y_t^{\text{model}}(j) - Y_t^{\text{stat}}(j)}{Y_t^{\text{stat}}(j)} \right|,$$

where $Y_t^{\text{model}}(j)$ is the output of complex j in year t evaluated by the model, and $Y_t^{\text{stat}}(j)$ is the corresponding official value, $j = 1, \dots, 4$, $\rho_j \in (-1, 0) \cup (0, +\infty)$.

The functional is nonlinear, non-convex, and may have multiple local minima; singularities also arise when some ρ_j approaches zero. We therefore use the following numerical procedure. First, local minima are searched on a logarithmic grid excluding neighborhoods of zero, with upper bound 20 and lower bound $-0.95 = -1 + 0.05$. Then, near each local minimum, an additional search is performed on a uniform grid. The step is decreased until 0.05, then the obtained values are compared and the minimum is selected.

The calibrated substitution elasticities are presented in Table 2. Perturbations of the calibrated parameters smaller than 0.05 produce only negligible changes in the criterion value, indicating stability of the estimates.

The calibrated elasticities demonstrate substantial heterogeneity across sectoral complexes. Manufacturing remains close to the Cobb-Douglas case, Exporting exhibits near-Leontief behavior with very limited substitution possibilities, while Infrastructure and Services demonstrate relatively high substitution elasticities.

Table 2. Calibration results: substitution elasticities of intermediate inputs for aggregated sectoral complexes of Kazakhstan

	Manufacturing	Exporting	Infrastructure	Services
Parameter ρ	0.19	12	-0.89	-0.58
Elasticity $\frac{1}{1 + \rho}$	0.84	0.07	9.5	2.3

3.5 Comparative Performance Analysis

We compare the reconstruction results of the nonlinear nested CD-CES input-output model with the linear Cobb-Douglas balance model using aggregated input-output statistics of Kazakhstan. The base-year table for 2023 is reproduced exactly in both models by construction. After calibration, both models are used to reconstruct equilibrium gross outputs of sectoral complexes for 2012-2024.

For each year and complex, we compute the relative deviation between reconstructed gross outputs and official statistical values. Table 3 reports average errors for the full interval 2012-2024, excluding the base year 2023.

Table 3. Average relative reconstruction errors of gross outputs, 2012-2024

Sectoral complex	Linear CD	Nonlinear nested CD-CES
Manufacturing	2.88%	2.88%
Exporting	3.07%	2.98%
Infrastructure	5.55%	3.85%
Services	2.50%	3.39%

For Manufacturing, Exporting, and Infrastructure, the nonlinear model provides reconstruction errors comparable to or lower than those of the linear CD specification over the full period 2012-2024.

For Services, the largest reconstruction errors of the both models correspond to 2012-2016, which are relatively distant from the the base year 2023. This indicates that both linear Cobb-Douglas and nonlinear CD-CES input-output models are mainly suitable for medium-term reconstruction. Although the nonlinear specification partially captures structural adjustment through endogenous prices and substitution effects, it still relies on fixed technological proportions and constant substitution parameters, whose accuracy decreases over long horizons, especially for rapidly transforming sectors.

For the medium-term interval corresponding to the calibration horizon, Table 4 presents average reconstruction errors for 2017-2020 and 2024.

Table 4. Average relative reconstruction errors of gross outputs, calibration period

Sectoral complex	Linear CD	Nonlinear nested CD-CES
Manufacturing	1.36%	1.44%
Exporting	3.21%	2.87%
Infrastructure	6.99%	3.59%
Services	2.34%	1.83%

On this interval, the nonlinear model reconstructs gross outputs of Exporting, Infrastructure, and Services more accurately than the linear Cobb-Douglas

specification. The strongest effect is observed for Infrastructure and Services, where substitution elasticities are relatively high.

For Manufacturing, the nonlinear model performs slightly worse than the linear Cobb-Douglas specification. This is consistent with the calibrated value $\rho \approx 0.19$, which is already close to the Cobb-Douglas case $\rho = 0$.

The years 2021-2022 were not used for calibration and correspond to the period affected by the COVID-19 shock and supply-chain disruptions. For these out-of-sample years, the nonlinear CD-CES model better captures the adjustment of Infrastructure and Services, while for Manufacturing and Exporting its reconstruction errors remain comparable to those of the linear Cobb-Douglas model. This result is consistent with the calibrated substitution elasticities: the strongest improvements are observed for sectoral complexes with more flexible substitution mechanisms.

The year 2020 demonstrates the specific sensitivity of the Services complex to rapid structural changes caused by mobility restrictions and organizational adjustment. Such effects are only partially captured by the current equilibrium substitution mechanisms and may require additional modeling constraints related to production capacities, labor availability, and logistics.

The results indicate that the nonlinear CD-CES input-output model becomes particularly important during periods of rapid changes in relative prices and production structure. Unlike the linear Cobb-Douglas balance with fixed financial proportions, the CD-CES framework allows endogenous restructuring of technological coefficients through price-induced substitution effects.

4 Conclusion

The paper develops a nonlinear input-output model with nested CD-CES production functions and applies it to aggregated input-output statistics of Kazakhstan. The framework formalizes competitive equilibrium in a production network through an optimal resource-allocation problem and a dual system of Young equilibrium price equations with endogenous technological coefficients.

The numerical experiments show that the nonlinear CD-CES model reconstructs medium-term production-network dynamics more accurately than the linear Cobb-Douglas balance for sectoral complexes characterized by more flexible substitution mechanisms. The improvement is especially visible for Infrastructure and Services and for the out-of-sample crisis years 2021-2022 associated with the COVID-19 shock. The results indicate that endogenous restructuring of technological coefficients through price-induced substitution effects becomes important under large external shocks and changing relative prices.

The calculations also show that both linear and nonlinear input-output models are mainly suitable for short- and medium-term analysis, where the technological structure remains sufficiently stable. In this setting, the nonlinear CD-CES model provides a more flexible description of production-network adjustment under changing relative prices.

At the same time, the results for the Services complex during the COVID-19 period indicate that rapid structural adjustment under large shocks may require additional equilibrium constraints related to labor availability, production capacities, and logistics. Further development of the nonlinear model in this direction is left for future research.

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Appendix

Notation: M - Manufacturing, E - Exporting, I - Infrastructure, S - Services; Fc - Final consumption, Tc - Total consumption, Tp - Total production; Im - Import, W - Wage, GS - GOS;

Table 5. Sectoral complexes and associated industries (system of national accounts classification, [14])

Sector	Associated numbers
M	1, 2, 3, 11, 14, 22, 27, 30, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36
E	4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28, 29, 31, 37, 38
I	39, 47, 48, 49, 50, 54, 55
S	40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 51, 52, 53, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68

Table 6. Aggregated symmetric input-output table of Kazakhstan, 2023, trln tenge

	M	E	I	S	Fc	Tc
M	2.52518	0.190017	0.0957517	1.52153	13.9947	18.3272
E	0.714609	9.69595	1.17882	3.9336	28.7557	44.2786
I	0.434905	2.28032	1.12278	4.74313	7.49812	16.0793
S	2.5889	5.69539	2.26611	19.633	73.0271	103.21
Im	2.26399	2.98606	1.27733	6.21563		
W	2.27652	6.43904	3.64972	24.4015		
GS	7.52311	16.9919	6.48874	42.7621		
Tp	18.3272	44.2786	16.0793	103.21		

Table 7. Scenario data for Kazakhstan, 2012-2024: price indices s and final consumption Z^0 , trln tenge

Year	Im: s_1	W: s_2	GOS: s_3	M: Z_1^0	E: Z_2^0	I: Z_3^0	S: Z_4^0
2012	0.33	0.29	0.37	3.206	11.348	3.422	14.477
2013	0.34	0.31	0.41	3.875	11.008	3.557	17.944
2014	0.40	0.34	0.43	4.176	12.276	4.128	19.700
2015	0.49	0.36	0.45	4.767	9.031	5.032	23.111
2016	0.75	0.41	0.51	5.509	11.664	5.473	27.295
2017	0.72	0.43	0.55	6.249	14.974	5.618	28.214
2018	0.76	0.46	0.60	7.100	18.188	6.205	32.285
2019	0.84	0.53	0.64	8.077	19.439	6.689	37.068
2020	0.91	0.61	0.68	9.909	16.686	5.902	40.173
2021	0.94	0.71	0.77	11.039	22.392	6.489	49.221
2022	1.02	0.88	0.91	13.655	31.909	7.357	56.462
2023	1.00	1.00	1.00	13.995	28.756	7.498	73.027
2024	1.03	1.13	1.08	15.154	29.355	9.147	86.232

Table 8. Relative reconstruction errors of gross outputs, %

Year	Linear Cobb-Douglas model				Nonlinear CD-CES model			
	M	E	I	S	M	E	I	S
2012	1.01	1.77	1.44	3.58	0.23	1.13	6.70	7.02
2013	2.74	5.21	5.52	4.60	2.08	4.86	0.53	7.39
2014	0.21	2.76	4.33	0.79	0.54	3.67	0.51	2.32
2015	0.19	0.39	4.45	0.22	0.89	1.58	1.30	3.69
2016	3.37	2.32	0.28	3.93	3.41	2.01	6.58	7.54
2017	3.26	2.23	4.36	2.68	3.63	1.42	2.13	1.19
2018	1.13	5.26	9.26	2.92	1.54	4.46	3.03	0.96
2019	0.26	1.47	10.55	1.37	0.12	1.07	6.14	1.35
2020	0.62	1.28	6.87	1.77	0.52	1.27	3.94	3.31
2021	8.50	6.81	10.82	2.85	8.52	6.68	8.84	1.79
2022	11.69	1.54	4.79	2.35	11.70	1.46	3.86	1.83
2023	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2024	1.53	5.80	3.92	2.98	1.41	6.14	2.70	2.34